

Supplemental materials of: Evolutionary lability of sexual selection and its implications for speciation and macroevolution

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Supplementary text Part SI: Sexual selection

One way to compare sexual selection among species is by using the intensity of selection, usually measured through the standardized selection differentials s' (whose units are pre-selection trait standard deviations). To measure the intensity of selection, we use the equation:

$$s' = \frac{(\overline{Z}_{t+\delta} - \overline{Z}_t)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(Z_t)}} \quad \text{Eq. S1}$$

Where z is the focal univariate, heritable trait, and subscripts denote time (t = pre-selection; $t+\delta$ denotes post-selection), the superscript bar denotes average, and the function “var()” denotes variance (Arnold, 2023 “Evolutionary quantitative genetics” - p. 12). Equation S1 only describes the intensity of selection with respect to the mean of a trait. However, it emphasizes that comparisons involving sexual selection intensity cannot occur “in the vacuum”: selection must (i) occur in a trait, and it must (ii) create a difference in the mean trait (pre vs post-selection, usually at generational timescales) for it to be detected. This is where most criticism of the opportunity for sexual selection comes from – assuming that the opportunity for selection and actual selection on a specific trait do in fact align, which is not guaranteed because the intensity of selection can end up not co-varying with the additive genetic variation in the trait. Additional complications arise when we consider that traits which are not affected by sexual selection can influence (i.e., bias or prevent) selection response, and thus the estimate of selection intensity.

Because clades vary in which traits they have, it would be meaningless to compare selection intensity across deeply diverging species (intense selection on feathers is meaningless to a fish). This is where the opportunity for selection is helpful, and arguably more meaningful to diversification/trait

evolution. Opportunity for selection indices measure the skewness in success (in mating, fertilization, etc depending on the index used) that may be associated with intrasexual competition for mates (i.e., sexual selection).

Importantly, if the variance of any trait is indeed co-varying with the opportunity for sexual selection (i.e., individuals with brighter feathers have more offspring), then the selection response will be proportional to the opportunity for sexual selection and the co-variance between opportunity and the selected trait. The opportunity for sexual selection is then an “all else being equal” univariate measure of the *potential* that a certain population has to respond to sexual selection (i.e., it is the upper bound of selection response). In other words, opportunity for selection measures the potential to respond to selection in any trait aligned with the actual “fitness currency” that sexual selection deals with access for mates (and their gametes). Opportunity for selection indices can in principle also vary stochastically through time within the same deme.

A demography-based analogous measure for natural selection would be an index of variance in survivorship up to the moment of reproduction (assuming every surviving individual would reproduce evenly after survival). Houle et al 2011, as well as Rios Moura and Peixoto 2013 provide additional arguments related to meaningfulness and comparability of the numerical scale of variables like the opportunity for sexual selection.

Supplementary text Part SII: The scale of speciation rate variation

Speciation rate values are unevenly distributed across clades, but this does not necessarily mean that understanding speciation requires full sampling of all species within a clade. In fact, unevenness in variation can be used to maximize analysis power in relation to sampling effort, and similar phenomena occur frequently in ecology studies. For instance, if one wants to study the variation of abiotic factors

within an intertidal zone in a beach where 75% of the area corresponds only to the lower intertidal zone, then stratified sampling can be used to maximize analysis power with a relatively small number of samples. What does the above metaphor have to do with speciation? When it comes to capturing variation in speciation rates within a sample of species, most closely related species will likely represent “pseudoreplicas” instead of true replicas (similarly to the samples taken within the same intertidal strata of the metaphor above). True replicas would then be distantly related clades that have enough phylogenetically independent variation in speciation rates.

To illustrate how speciation co-varies at broad taxonomic scales, we downloaded (from GBIF, using the R package *taxize* (Chamberlain & Szöcs 2013) the taxonomic families for every species in the original speciation rate dataset (From Cooney & Thomas 2021, containing all tip speciation rates - not just the ones evaluated empirically in our manuscript). We couldn't find the family for 286 tips, so we dropped them in this short analysis (whose result is contingent on *taxize*'s accuracy).

First, we used deviance tables (i.e., analysis of variance) to measure the percentage of residuals associated with different taxonomic levels: (I) clade (amphibian, bird, squamate, mammal, ray-finned fish), (II) taxonomic families and (III) genus. Supplementary Table 7 supports the view that a large proportion of speciation rates varies at higher taxonomic scales (clade + family = 51% of variance explained), not within them (genus explains ~ 30% of variation, and ~18% is residual variation). This can also be visualized in Supplementary figure 11, where the variation in speciation rate (in both λ_{BAMM} and λ_{DR}) is associated with clade and family is shown.

This can also be visualized in any large (>300 spp.) vertebrate phylogeny that is more than 70% complete (so speciation measure is accurate - Chang et al 2020) and in which speciation rates estimated with methods like BAMM, CLaDS, etc and plotted on every branch (closely related tips will have very similar values in these cases).

Supplementary text Part SIII: Negative Bateman

Gradients

Bateman gradients measure the fitness returns associated with each mating event (∇_{ms}) or reproductive partner (∇_{fs}). Thus, negative Bateman gradients indicate that individuals obtain fitness benefits by mating *less*, which in turn is ambiguous evidence for one of two scenarios we speculate on: (A) natural selection exceeding sexual selection to a point of erasing its quantitative evidence (given the potential for these forces to oppose each other - e.g., Heinemann-Kay *et al*, 2015; Okada *et al*, 2021; and references therein), or (B) choosier individuals being sexually selected because of the cost of multiple matings (see Burke & Bonduriansky, 2017, and references therein). The former has little information about sexual selection (our focus here). The second sharply contrasts with traditional sexual selection theory, which historically assesses the fitness return of multiple matings, not the opposite (see Darwin, 1871; Bateman, 1948; Dewsbury, 2005; Slatyer *et al*, 2012). Because in our manuscript we are interested in proxies to sexual selection intensity, we removed negative Bateman gradients from our analysis.

Number of effective sizes removed: five females and one male for ∇_{fs} , and two females and zero males removed for ∇_{ms} .

Supplementary text Part SIV: Power in comparative analyses of speciation.

How does the autocorrelation in speciation among closely related species (see supplementary text Part SII, above) affects power in comparative analyses of speciation? We show this more clearly below,

by repeating our first power analysis (that models power as a sigmoidal curve), but instead of using the tips within our dataset, we run our power analysis in 577 families of vertebrates that have between 4 and 250 species. Our aim is to compare the power of our results with the power that we would have had if we have sampled a family-level vertebrate clade.

The Supplementary figure 13 shows the result of this analysis and supports the view that increasing the evolutionary-independent variation within the data increases statistical power. In the family-level analyses, most clades have no statistical power (white bars, Supplementary Figure 13). It is straightforward to think that sampling within a single clade does not necessarily answer questions about phylogenetic speciation rates more broadly. However, less trivial is the fact that many single clades (e.g., one family) usually do not provide adequate statistical power in most comparative analyses of speciation (white bars, Supplementary Figure 13). This is particularly problematic for speciation studies because a large part of the comparative literature “measures sexual selection” through traits, and so this literature is inherently restricted to always assessing smaller speciation rate variation (see Supplementary figures 1, 7, 11, and 13). This is a major strength of phylogenetically-overdispersed analyses like the one we employ in the main text of our study: most traits are shared only by a restricted set of species, but all species have populations, and if we can extract demographic information from these populations (e.g., with opportunity for selection indices), we can explore questions about speciation at the scale where most of the variation exists.

Supplementary text Part SV: Details of clade-level

PGLS analyses

See Supplementary tables 8 & 9.

Results on sexual selection and speciation rate

Clade-specific analyses for the full dataset show 4 significant clade-specific relationships (out of 69 tested) between selection indices and speciation rates, all of which are not consistent among different analyses (Supplementary Tables 1 & 6). In the clade-specific analyses using the zero-only dataset, only three (out of 49) were significant, but those were not consistent (Supplementary Tables 2 & 6).

Results on Sexual selection and proxy traits

In the clade-specific analyses we were able to make in the full dataset, only three out of 38 SSD analyses (and only amphibian female ϕ_f correlates negatively with λ_{BAMM}), and none of the 20 dichromatism analyses, were significant. For the zero-only dataset, we found significant results in only one (out of 28) SSD analyses. None of the six dichromatism analyses we were able to run in the zero-only dataset were significant.

Supplementary text Part SVI: “Local” measurements of phylogenetic signal

We tested whether phylogenetic signal differed among clades by quantifying tip-specific deviations from the “background” phylogenetic signal using a framework based on Keck et al (2016), hereafter referred to as LIPA (which is equivalent to Moran’s I (Moran, 1950; Gittleman & Kot, 1990)). This approach is a model-free indicator of phylogenetic association between a tip and its closely related lineages (positive values meaning more association – i.e., signal – and negative values less association compared to the background phylogenetic signal). Significance for each tip is based on the limits of the 95% quantile region from a null pseudo-distribution of LIPA values generated for each tip. Pseudo-distributions are generated by permutations of trait values at the tips and subsequent re-calculation of tip-specific LIPA values.

In our tests for heterogeneity in phylogenetic signal itself (Supplementary Figure 13), tips that deviate from the background phylogenetic signal usually do so only for specific combinations of sex, species, and index, meaning it is unlikely that some clades distort the overall pattern of phylogenetic signal. The clades that seem to more consistently deviate from this “background” phylogenetic signal are Passeriform birds, but this result is not consistent across indices and sexes (Supplementary Figure 12). Comparisons among the lineages that deviate from the background phylogenetic signal (i.e., the “significant lineages in Supplementary Figure 12) and other closely related clades could be possible starting points in further investigations of this topic, conditioned in the data and the indices evaluated here (which, we advise, might be a very incomplete representation of which clades really deviate most from the background vertebrate patterns).

Supplementary text Part SVII: Extinction and sexual selection

Even though we found that speciation rates and opportunity for sexual selection are uncorrelated, a different (and also meta-analytic) investigation (Janicke *et al*, 2018) found an association between selection indices and clade richness in animals as a whole (see also Ellis & Oakley, 2016). There are many unresolved issues with respect to the relationship between species richness patterns and diversification rates (Rabosky & Benson, 2021) so further explorations of how sexual selection impacts diversification are still needed in biodiversity theory. An unexplored research inquiry at the core of this issue is the effect of sexual selection on extinction rates, which jointly with speciation generate heterogeneous diversification (and richness) among clades. Although sexual selection is largely assumed to positively impact the probability of speciation, at least some theoretical literature suggests that – under some scenarios – intense sexual selection might also result in increased extinction probability (Promislow *et al*, 1992; Tanaka 1996; Kokko & Brooks, 2003; Doherty *et al*, 2003). Consequently, understanding

how sexual selection interacts with population density, population persistence, and global extinction is a critical and unresolved problem in biodiversity theory. The scarce empirical evidence for this relationship comes from fossil lineages whose sexual size dimorphism is positively correlated with extinction probability (Martins et al, 2018), and from a study where sexually dichromatic bird species have higher extirpation rates on islands (Doherty et al, 2003). However, our results suggest that caution is needed when interpreting these and other proxy-based conclusions about sexual selection and extinction, as we found no relationship between the opportunity for sexual selection and SSD or bird dichromatism. Moreover, one can hypothesize that intense sexual selection alone is unlikely to frequently cause extinctions, as selection intensity should decrease following population density declines, when individuals become less choosy. Furthermore, multiple studies have found that the expression of sexually selected traits is positively associated with individual survivorship (Jennions et al, 2001), again suggesting that the connection between extinction and sexual selection is tenuous. Indeed, Rowe and Rundle (2021) question whether it is even possible to properly address empirically the relationship between the intensity of sexual selection and extinction due to the difficulty of studying each of the two variables – studying the relationship between both, then, seems a distant enterprise. Consequently, the consequences of sexual selection intensity to diversification remain poorly understood.

Supplementary Figures:

Figure S1: The importance of including distantly related species in analyses of speciation. Because closely related species (e.g., taxonomic families, shown by point shape) usually present small phylogenetically-independent variation in speciation rates (represented by colors), analyses involving traits that are shared only within the same family (e.g., dewlap color) are inherently restricted to consider only a small fraction of variation in speciation rates. Analyses that involve species from disparate clades (i.e., that are “phylogenetically-overdispersed”, panels F & G), can utilize much more variation in speciation rates, and thus can potentially have larger statistical power – even when they include relatively few species.

Figure S2. PRISMA diagram, showing the steps employed here to obtain estimates of the intensity of sexual selection on non-human Osteichthyes under field conditions. For details see Macedo-Rego et al 2024.

Figure S3. Correlation among log-transformed (base 2) indices for males (averaged by species). Solid black lines indicate PGLS whose slope differs significantly from zero and dashed gray lines refer to non-significant PGLS slopes. Point color and symbols refer to clades and follow the legend of the main text. P-values assigned as zero represent comparisons where $p < 0.0001$ that were rounded for visualization purposes. Please note that plots are mirrored around the main diagonal of the panel to facilitate visual comparisons. Plots without points represent PGLS which could not be fit to data (usually due to sample size, which is shown). Note that although no analyzed index seems to correlate with male ∇_{ms} , we hypothesize this could be caused by the small sample size, which is relatively more affected by the two squamate points (green open triangles), which seem to have an inverted (negative) relationship, while all other clades show positive relationships among indices, meaning we still believe that broadly speaking all indices of sexual selection are correlated. The dataset shown is the full dataset (i.e., including populations in which we are unsure zero-success individuals were reported).

Figure S4. Correlation among log-transformed (base 2) indices for females (averaged by species). Solid black lines indicate PGLS whose slope differs significantly from zero and dashed gray lines refer to non-significant PGLS. Point color and symbols refer to clades and follow the legend of the main text. P-values assigned as zero represent comparisons where $p < 0.0001$, which we rounded for visualization purposes. Please note that plots are mirrored around the main diagonal of the panel to facilitate visual comparisons. Plots without points represent PGLS which could not be fit to data (usually due to sample size, which is shown). The dataset shown is the full dataset (i.e., includes populations in which we are unsure zero-success individuals were reported).

Figure S5: Population-specific Bateman gradient estimates are biased towards smaller values when the R^2 of the linear model that calculated them is low. The dataset shown is the full dataset (i.e., including populations in which we are unsure zero-success individuals were reported). Each panel shows population-specific values - which should not be confused with the averaged values per species that are used in most analyses and shown in most plots of our study.

Figure S6: No relationship between sexual selection intensity and speciation rates as measured by λ_{BAMM} (full dataset). Points show species-sex-specific averages. All other models in this plot do not explain the data better (i.e., PGLS with $\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) than a null model with the intercept term alone (black dashed lines). We could not run the model where λ_{BAMM} is a function of female ∇_{ms} (panel D, no line shown). Point colors and shapes refer to vertebrate orders, legend: red open circle = amphibians; yellow filled circle = birds; open blue square = fishes, pink filled triangle = mammals; green open triangle = squamates. Black lines show each PGLS (parameter estimates shown in Supplementary Table 1).

Figure S7: Power analyses estimated threshold (estimated in power analysis 1), as a function of analysis sample size (i.e., number of species) for all PGLS conducted. A horizontal continuous line (threshold value = 1) separates powerless analyses (points above the line) from the rest. A horizontal dashed line (threshold value = 0.3) separates analysis with power to detect moderate-to-small power (below dashed line) from the analyses that need moderate-to-large true correlations for a true signal to be detected (above dashed line, below continuous line). Panels separate analyses from different datasets as well as analyses that correlate indices with speciation rate or with proxy traits. Note the vertebrate-level analyses with more than 30 species have substantially more power than the order-specific analyses.

Figure S8: Intraspecific variation in sexual selection intensity across different metrics (A - J) for individual species. Horizontal bars represent species range, smaller points represent population-level observations. Gray points represent species means. Gray boxplots at the top of each panel show the entire distribution across all vertebrate populations for the corresponding index. The range of variability within individual species is so high that many species span much of the entire range of values seen across all vertebrates. Point colors and shapes refer to vertebrate orders, as in Figure 3. Females of one species (*Anaxyrus americanus*) have only zero-valued ϕ_{Is} , so they do not appear in panel F. Species with only one sampled population are not shown individually but are included in the boxplot. Lines do not match among panels, and panel names (A-J) do not match those in Figure 3 (main text).

Figure S9: Illustration of the binomial model (P_{signif}) used in Power analysis I. Each point represents the qualitative result of PGLS between a simulated trait that is correlated with speciation rate (i.e., trait-speciation $R^2 = \rho$ (x-axis in all plots)). Points are assigned as significant or non-significant (y-axis in all plots, emphasized by point color). Thus, the binomial model describes the probability a given speciation and phylogeny have to detect a true correlation, giving the simulated value of ρ . In the set of panels A, it is illustrated how the two parameters “r” (“rate of increase”) and “t” (correlation “threshold”) summarize this test power. All parameters in the binomial model describe the change in statistical power as a function of ρ . However, as shown in the set of panels B, the overall results are dominated by the values of the parameter “t” (threshold), which represents the value of true correlation that, if present, has at least 50% chance to be detected, given a phylogeny and the tip values of the dependent variable (speciation rate or trait). Because 1.0 is the upper bound of any correlation coefficient, power analyses with its estimated “t” being larger than 1.0 (panel B.IV) represent analyses based on virtually powerless sets of species (given the provided phylogeny and speciation rates).

Figure S10: Phylogenetic signal of the opportunity for selection indices, for traditional sexual selection proxies, and for a reference set of traits from Blomberg et al (2003) that span a range of organismal functions. Colors and shapes show vertebrate groups where signal was measured, showing no clade-specific phylogenetic signal values. Boxplots highlight interquartile differences among distributions. The horizontal continuous line shows the phylogenetic signal expected under Brownian motion, and the horizontal dashed line shows phylogenetic signal in body weight (average of the two sexes) calculated using the same data compiled for the dimorphism analyses and the phylogeny used in all analyses. Kappa estimates are log-transformed for visualization purposes.

Figure S11: Taxonomic distribution of speciation rates. The X-axis shows vertebrate families (sorted by median speciation rate), and the y-values in the boxplots show species-specific speciation rates. Panels and colors show clades. Species within the same family tend to have more similar speciation rates, and the pattern is stronger for λ_{BMM} when compared to λ_{DR} .

Figure S12: Tip-specific phylogenetic signal for all sexual selection indices, separated by sex (circles for females, squares for males; full dataset shown). Values of LIPA close to zero (yellow) follow the “background” index-sex-specific phylogenetic signal. Positive values (red) show tips with relatively (to background) stronger phylogenetic signal to their closely related lineages, while negative values (blue) refer to tips that represent a local reduction in phylogenetic signal. Black frame in point shows significant LIPA values. Acknowledgments section show silhouette credits.

Figure S13: Statistical power in “typical” (Vertebrate families, see Supplementary text Part SIV) and phylogenetically-overdispersed (i.e., the datasets used in the analyses in the main text) analyses of speciation rate. The black histograms show the number of analyses in different power bins (i.e., threshold parameter in our power analyses), while the white bars show the number of analyses with no power (out of the scale in the x-axis but still on scale in the y-axis). Percentage of analyses with some power: Family-level = 13.7%; Full dataset, all clades = 90%; Full dataset, clade-level analyses = 55.4%; Zero-only dataset, all clades = 83.3%; Zero-only dataset, clade-level analyses: 37%. Ordered quartiles: Family-level: 25% = 0.257, median = 0.461, 75% = 0.600; Full dataset (all clades): 25% = 0.090, median = 0.153, 75% = 0.220; Full dataset (clade-level analyses): 25% = 0.295, median = 0.417, 75% = 0.607; Zero-only dataset (all clades): 25% = 0.108, median = 0.167, 75% = 0.207; Zero-only dataset, (clade-level analyses): 25% = 0.332, median = 0.537, 75% = 0.630.

Figure S14: Illustrative examples of correlations between proxy traits (upper row = weight SSD; lower row = Dichromatism index based on color discriminability) and opportunity for sexual selection (ϕ_1). Panels show correlations for both sexes (left column = males, right column = females). These cases were chosen because they represent comparisons made with more species in our dataset, and they all represent our qualitative result (no correlation is significant). Comparisons made with the “full dataset” (see main text for details). Black points in the bottom row show two species of North American passeriform birds with interesting patterns of opportunity-proxy: the dichromatic red-winged blackbird (*Agelaius phoeniceus*, diamonds) and the “less dichromatic” white-crowned sparrow (*Zonotrichia leucophrys*, black squares). Although these two species differ considerably in dichromatism, their opportunity for sexual selection is not relatively consistent among sexes (x axis in the bottom row panels), and the males of the dichromatic species have a less skewed variance in reproductive success (lower left panel, smaller opportunity for selection). Females of the dichromatic red-winged blackbird seem to experience stronger opportunity for selection when compared to the females of the “less dichromatic” white-crowned sparrow.

Supplementary tables from Macroevolutionary liability decouples sexual selection intensity from speciation rate and trait evolution of bony vertebrates

Table S1. PGLS results for each combination of speciation rate as a function of selection index for the full dataset. Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	BAMM	Is	Males	21	-2.837	-0.01	0.0036	0.3302	-0.3782	0.0512	0.4061
All	DR	Is	Males	21	-2.536	0.055	0.0137	0.1617	-0.2173	0.0074	0.2078
All	BAMM	I	Males	62	-2.993	0.034	0.0118	0.1277	-0.2237	0.0153	0.2105
All	DR	I	Males	62	-3.321	0.089	0.0115	0.0445	-0.0824	-0.0098	0.0718
All	BAMM	If	Males	53	-2.989	0.005	0.0003	0.1414	-0.2169	0.0020	0.2131
All	DR	If	Males	53	-3.408	-0.008	0.0001	0.0614	-0.0928	0.0039	0.0927
All	BAMM	Bgm	Males	6	-2.589	0.207	0.0143	0.8128	-0.5698	0.0598	0.6206
All	DR	Bgm	Males	6	-2.685	-0.018	0.0001	0.5428	-0.4710	-0.0172	0.4384
All	BAMM	Bgf	Males	36	-2.917	0.154	0.0389	0.1912	-0.2928	0.0302	0.3044
All	DR	Bgf	Males	36	-3.224	0.113	0.0025	0.0814	-0.1123	0.0056	0.1146
All	BAMM	Is	Females	15	-2.980	0.012	0.0011	0.3414	-0.3458	-0.0042	0.3312
All	DR	Is	Females	15	-3.476	-0.214	0.0868	0.1849	-0.2202	-0.0112	0.2160
All	BAMM	I	Females	55	-2.832	0.008	0.0009	0.1451	-0.2191	-0.0100	0.2247
All	DR	I	Females	55	-3.347	0.03	0.0020	0.0686	-0.0988	0.0073	0.0935
All	BAMM	If	Females	48	-2.785	0.05	0.0121	0.1612	-0.2482	0.0158	0.2459
All	DR	If	Females	48	-3.299	0.012	0.0002	0.0778	-0.1054	0.0244	0.1390
All	BAMM	Bgm	Females	3	—	—	—	16.3177	—	—	—
All	DR	Bgm	Females	3	—	—	—	10.9419	—	—	—
All	BAMM	Bgf	Females	32	-2.893	-0.009	0.0011	0.2304	-0.3266	0.0048	0.3036
All	DR	Bgf	Females	32	-3.485	0.014	0.0003	0.1162	-0.1560	-0.0007	0.1610
Fish	BAMM	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Males	11	-2.381	0.079	0.0640	0.6054	-0.5511	0.0520	0.6067
Fish	DR	I	Males	11	-3.478	-0.073	0.0520	0.2957	-0.3235	0.0114	0.2838
Fish	BAMM	If	Males	11	-2.337	0.044	0.0232	0.6150	-0.5618	-0.0520	0.5637
Fish	DR	If	Males	11	-3.505	-0.065	0.0265	0.2728	-0.2357	0.0169	0.3014
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-2.401	0.007	0.0003	0.6057	-0.5867	0.0639	0.5436
Fish	DR	Bgf	Males	9	-3.648	-0.319	0.1566	0.3573	-0.4282	-0.0180	0.4151
Fish	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Females	10	-2.160	0.053	0.0258	0.7725	-0.6668	-0.0106	0.6779
Fish	DR	I	Females	10	-3.392	0.266	0.2118	0.3602	-0.4760	-0.0501	0.4736
Fish	BAMM	If	Females	10	-1.977	0.132	0.0980	5.7982	-0.6727	-0.0292	0.6956
Fish	DR	If	Females	10	-3.287	0.165	0.0595	0.3918	-0.4163	-0.0269	0.3614
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Females	7	-2.160	-0.004	0.0000	5.4283	-0.6116	-0.0447	0.6826
Fish	DR	Bgf	Females	7	-3.490	0.884*	0.6248	0.7174	-0.8311	0.3012	0.8223
Birds	BAMM	Is	Males	6	-2.668	0.054	0.0615	7.2239	-0.6881	-0.0432	0.6814
Birds	DR	Is	Males	6	-1.550	0.884*†	0.7468	0.4959	-0.8045	-0.0238	0.8081
Birds	BAMM	I	Males	17	-3.089	0.057	0.0431	0.5511	-0.5796	-0.0014	0.6075
Birds	DR	I	Males	17	-3.412	0.365	0.0960	0.1653	-0.2481	0.0090	0.2182
Birds	BAMM	If	Males	15	-3.076	-0.014	0.0051	0.6075	-0.6348	-0.0127	0.6061
Birds	DR	If	Males	15	-3.462	-0.102	0.0117	0.2185	-0.2262	0.0311	0.2544
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-3.008	0.369	0.2395	6.7898	-0.8344	-0.0714	0.7900
Birds	DR	Bgf	Males	9	—	—	—	0.3427	—	—	—

Table S1. PGLS results for each combination of speciation rate (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Birds	BAMM	Is	Females	4	-2.628	0.293	0.2037	8.2440	-0.7793	-0.0511	0.6888
Birds	DR	Is	Females	4	-1.566	0.815	0.4245	4.9944	-0.6788	0.0837	0.6214
Birds	BAMM	I	Females	16	-3.063	0.001	0.0000	0.6009	-0.6230	-0.0040	0.6553
Birds	DR	I	Females	16	-3.357	0.084	0.0243	0.2612	-0.3385	0.0011	0.3129
Birds	BAMM	If	Females	14	-3.047	0.009	0.0004	0.6200	-0.5902	-0.0116	0.5779
Birds	DR	If	Females	14	-2.809	0.298	0.0632	0.3328	-0.3807	-0.0027	0.4020
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Females	10	-3.104	-0.007	0.0019	6.7757	-0.7496	-0.0256	0.6804
Birds	DR	Bgf	Females	10	-2.975	-0.069	0.0259	0.4165	-0.3925	-0.0223	0.4490
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Males	3	-2.389	0.445	0.8827	9.8723	-0.9447	-0.0512	0.9533
Squamates	DR	Is	Males	3	-3.036	0.326	0.3457	11.1928	-0.6680	0.0077	0.6450
Squamates	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.220	0.015	0.0011	6.2964	-0.5757	0.0052	0.6089
Squamates	DR	I	Males	6	-3.123	-0.082	0.0096	0.6195	-0.6005	0.0313	0.5659
Squamates	BAMM	If	Males	6	-3.217	-0.07	0.0709	6.7299	-0.6383	0.0117	0.6197
Squamates	DR	If	Males	6	-3.219	-0.239	0.2114	0.6349	-0.6013	0.0373	0.6330
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	12.0525	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	15.4268	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Females	3	-2.505	0.198	0.3006	11.2164	-0.7344	0.0471	0.7941
Squamates	DR	Is	Females	3	-3.428	-0.005	0.0002	8.9295	-0.5694	0.0032	0.5035
Squamates	BAMM	I	Females	7	-3.192	-0.015	0.0074	6.0460	-0.6310	-0.0226	0.6084
Squamates	DR	I	Females	7	-3.223	-0.092	0.0638	0.5484	-0.5219	-0.0218	0.4708
Squamates	BAMM	If	Females	6	-3.249	-0.039	0.0314	7.1499	-0.6173	0.0402	0.6555
Squamates	DR	If	Females	6	-3.395	-0.201	0.2048	0.6618	-0.5969	-0.0064	0.6896
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	11.2164	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	15.6436	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Males	3	-3.911	1.043*	1.0000	14.6264	-0.9901	0.0548	0.9866
Amphibians	DR	Is	Males	3	-3.343	0.913	0.6210	12.1568	-0.8625	0.0447	0.8065
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Males	8	-3.832	0.142	0.2114	0.6921	-0.7003	-0.0420	0.6698
Amphibians	DR	I	Males	8	-4.332	0.02	0.0024	0.5111	-0.4602	0.0110	0.4498
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Males	6	-3.861	0.035	0.0140	8.3464	-0.6799	0.0008	0.7183
Amphibians	DR	If	Males	6	-4.576	0.043	0.0124	6.2260	-0.6950	-0.0409	0.6922
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Males	5	-3.446	2.071	0.1387	8.8012	-0.7998	0.0115	0.7887
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Males	5	-4.703	-4.85	0.3403	9.0906	-0.8588	0.0278	0.8466
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Females	7	-3.900	-0.306*	0.7222	5.2901	-0.9379	0.1862	0.9389
Amphibians	DR	I	Females	7	-4.589	-0.331	0.3592	0.6086	-0.7144	0.0181	0.7373
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Females	5	-3.776	-0.121	0.2788	9.7710	-0.7552	0.0071	0.8392
Amphibians	DR	If	Females	5	-4.431	-0.129	0.1854	9.1424	-0.7678	0.0712	0.7887
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Females	5	-3.749	-0.095	0.1033	10.2192	-0.7770	-0.0374	0.7981
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Females	5	-4.727	-0.343	0.7565	8.5354	-0.9552	0.1588	0.9409
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Males	9	-1.806	-0.022	0.0646	9.0667	-0.7836	-0.0717	0.7717
Mammals	DR	Is	Males	9	-1.891	0.057	0.0648	0.5639	-0.5362	0.0589	0.5788
Mammals	BAMM	I	Males	20	-2.534	0.002	0.0000	0.2789	-0.3217	0.0138	0.3228
Mammals	DR	I	Males	20	-2.334	0.176	0.0284	0.1184	-0.1462	-0.0010	0.1494
Mammals	BAMM	If	Males	15	-2.524	0.057	0.0111	0.2856	-0.3346	0.0114	0.3725
Mammals	DR	If	Males	15	-2.512	0.487	0.1335	0.1677	-0.2333	-0.0469	0.2076
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Males	10	-2.634	2.089	0.3019	0.5549	-0.6509	0.0750	0.7779
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Males	10	-3.240	1.052	0.0302	0.3415	-0.3179	0.0145	0.3531
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Females	6	-1.942	-0.055	0.0555	10.2196	-0.7565	0.0771	0.7582
Mammals	DR	Is	Females	6	-3.501	-0.462	0.6233	5.4178	-0.8407	-0.1930	0.8547
Mammals	BAMM	I	Females	15	-2.529	0.037	0.0113	0.3000	-0.3376	-0.0083	0.3391
Mammals	DR	I	Females	15	-2.734	0.083	0.0168	0.1700	-0.2013	-0.0079	0.2184
Mammals	BAMM	If	Females	13	-2.363	0.129	0.0529	0.3194	-0.3382	0.0080	0.3568
Mammals	DR	If	Females	13	-2.115	0.448	0.2156	0.1942	-0.3236	-0.0283	0.2839
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Females	7	-2.643	-1.167	0.1013	0.7453	-0.6705	-0.0663	0.6070
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Females	7	-3.665	-5.515	0.5512	0.4179	-0.6445	0.1263	0.6617

Table S2. PGLS results for each combination of speciation rate as a function of selection index for the dataset that only includes studies with clear reporting of zero-success individuals. Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	BAMM	Is	Males	16	-2.935	-0.002	0.0003	0.4321	-0.5299	0.0340	0.5056
All	DR	Is	Males	16	-2.718	0.134	0.0598	0.1815	-0.2676	-0.0202	0.2246
All	BAMM	I	Males	42	-2.875	0.029	0.0082	0.1529	-0.2318	0.0057	0.2145
All	DR	I	Males	42	-3.249	0.032	0.0012	0.0515	-0.0566	0.0019	0.0899
All	BAMM	If	Males	34	-2.853	-0.001	0.0000	0.1671	-0.1971	0.0265	0.2357
All	DR	If	Males	34	-3.239	-0.137	0.0113	0.0721	-0.1206	-0.0009	0.1048
All	BAMM	Bgm	Males	4	-2.847	-1.039	0.3380	8.2447	-0.7720	-0.0993	0.7647
All	DR	Bgm	Males	4	-3.283	-1.933	0.3922	1.0861	-0.6102	-0.0371	0.6006
All	BAMM	Bgf	Males	25	-2.834	2.547*†	0.2207	0.2146	-0.3889	0.1437	0.3856
All	DR	Bgf	Males	25	-3.252	0.924	0.0136	0.1068	-0.1343	0.0279	0.1341
All	BAMM	Is	Females	5	-2.346	0.017	0.0020	5.8186	-0.6583	0.0233	0.6102
All	DR	Is	Females	5	-3.502	-0.23	0.2641	0.6044	-0.6046	0.0053	0.6054
All	BAMM	I	Females	25	-2.743	-0.03	0.0030	0.1995	-0.2342	0.0222	0.2466
All	DR	I	Females	25	-3.090	-0.002	0.0000	0.0973	-0.1476	0.0134	0.1286
All	BAMM	If	Females	23	-2.754	0.025	0.0013	0.1933	-0.2621	0.0084	0.2400
All	DR	If	Females	23	-3.135	0.062	0.0038	0.1108	-0.1417	-0.0153	0.1293
All	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	BAMM	Bgf	Females	18	-2.905	0.139	0.0105	0.2684	-0.2903	-0.0028	0.3297
All	DR	Bgf	Females	18	-3.563	0.049	0.0008	0.1626	-0.1785	-0.0436	0.1693
Birds	BAMM	Is	Males	4	-2.790	0.109	0.2769	13.1408	-0.8837	-0.0026	0.8888
Birds	DR	Is	Males	4	-1.768	0.525*†	0.9940	4.7379	-0.9862	-0.3352	0.9810
Birds	BAMM	I	Males	9	—	—	—	0.7479	—	—	—
Birds	DR	I	Males	9	—	—	—	0.1869	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	If	Males	7	—	—	—	6.8433	—	—	—
Birds	DR	If	Males	7	—	—	—	0.2694	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Males	4	-2.838	-0.708	0.0167	10.9030	-0.7494	0.0622	0.7526
Birds	DR	Bgf	Males	4	-0.562	14.418	0.2853	0.6108	-0.4675	0.0187	0.4182
Birds	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	I	Females	6	-2.700	0.026	0.0160	10.2312	-0.7821	-0.0584	0.7236
Birds	DR	I	Females	6	-1.979	0.385	0.3601	0.5457	-0.5933	0.1548	0.6651
Birds	BAMM	If	Females	5	-2.534	0.127	0.0872	10.2329	-0.7557	-0.0686	0.7515
Birds	DR	If	Females	5	-1.018	0.914	0.4025	0.6259	-0.6595	0.0495	0.6638
Birds	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	BAMM	Bgf	Females	4	-2.768	0.013	0.0009	12.9924	-0.7718	0.0556	0.8099
Birds	DR	Bgf	Females	4	-2.334	0.587	0.1623	5.8247	-0.5089	-0.0316	0.5764
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	I	Males	5	-3.612	0.301	0.5928	8.8201	-0.8949	0.1384	0.8974
Squamates	DR	I	Males	5	-3.761	0.19	0.1653	8.6523	-0.7146	-0.0361	0.6674
Squamates	BAMM	If	Males	5	-3.419	0.213	0.4876	9.9616	-0.8870	0.1062	0.8674
Squamates	DR	If	Males	5	-3.662	0.199	0.2309	8.2022	-0.7736	0.0574	0.7774
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	12.1701	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Males	3	—	—	—	16.3564	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	I	Females	4	-3.255	0.003	0.0001	10.5977	-0.7743	0.0494	0.7350
Squamates	DR	I	Females	4	-3.329	-0.202	0.4272	9.9653	-0.7874	-0.0928	0.8551
Squamates	BAMM	If	Females	4	-3.262	0.04	0.0115	9.2028	-0.7345	0.0066	0.7059
Squamates	DR	If	Females	4	-3.325	-0.189	0.3475	9.3922	-0.7736	0.1442	0.8060
Squamates	BAMM	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	BAMM	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	13.3471	—	—	—
Squamates	DR	Bgf	Females	3	—	—	—	14.8565	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.815	0.125	0.2840	6.1164	-0.7448	-0.0991	0.7827
Amphibians	DR	I	Males	6	-4.236	-0.014	0.0028	0.6323	-0.4821	-0.0390	0.4455
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Males	4	-3.569	-0.146	0.1390	9.5132	-0.7876	0.0109	0.8045
Amphibians	DR	If	Males	4	-4.728	0.176	0.1880	10.3538	-0.7479	0.0860	0.7991
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S2. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Speciation rate	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Males	4	-3.477	3.39	0.3385	10.8387	-0.7995	0.0418	0.8819
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Males	4	-4.773	-2.59	0.1337	11.7848	-0.7946	-0.0408	0.8190
Amphibians	BAMM	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	I	Females	5	-3.824	-0.334*	0.8150	6.8801	-0.9344	-0.0595	0.9251
Amphibians	DR	I	Females	5	-4.667	-0.375	0.5193	0.6481	-0.7273	0.1038	0.7121
Amphibians	BAMM	If	Females	4	-3.811	-0.11	0.2409	10.9086	-0.8270	0.0609	0.8212
Amphibians	DR	If	Females	4	-4.653	-0.034	0.0160	10.7098	-0.8221	0.0030	0.8151
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	BAMM	Bgf	Females	4	-3.740	-0.073	0.0097	12.8154	-0.7801	-0.0550	0.7668
Amphibians	DR	Bgf	Females	4	-4.827	-0.637	0.7281	14.0792	-0.9508	-0.1086	0.9226
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Males	8	-1.851	-0.018	0.0432	8.5216	-0.7866	0.0476	0.8223
Mammals	DR	Is	Males	8	-1.803	0.05	0.0472	0.5758	-0.5390	-0.0258	0.5143
Mammals	BAMM	I	Males	16	-2.436	-0.021	0.0051	0.3301	-0.3537	-0.0501	0.3664
Mammals	DR	I	Males	16	-2.291	0.09	0.0068	0.1362	-0.1514	-0.0174	0.1618
Mammals	BAMM	If	Males	12	-2.406	-0.019	0.0012	0.3378	-0.3600	-0.0399	0.2837
Mammals	DR	If	Males	12	-2.404	0.642	0.1114	0.2029	-0.2197	-0.0290	0.2389
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Males	9	-2.651	2.19	0.3229	0.5780	-0.7203	-0.0260	0.7057
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Males	9	-3.495	1.889	0.1604	0.4859	-0.5352	-0.0115	0.5675
Mammals	BAMM	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	I	Females	8	-2.490	0.119	0.0818	0.5298	-0.5438	-0.0301	0.5050
Mammals	DR	I	Females	8	-3.475	0.495	0.3698	0.3022	-0.4456	0.0633	0.4426
Mammals	BAMM	If	Females	8	-2.163	-0.141	0.0316	0.4962	-0.4262	0.0151	0.4812
Mammals	DR	If	Females	8	-2.957	0.137	0.0129	0.3587	-0.2947	0.0165	0.3126
Mammals	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	BAMM	Bgf	Females	5	-2.979	-0.04	0.0001	9.3278	-0.6715	0.0171	0.6858
Mammals	DR	Bgf	Females	5	-4.037	0.318	0.0016	5.0396	-0.5795	-0.0229	0.5680
Fish	BAMM	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Males	6	-3.011	0.666*	0.6980	0.7006	-0.8379	-0.1322	0.8920
Fish	DR	I	Males	6	-3.640	-0.146	0.0750	5.7105	-0.6609	-0.0236	0.6760
Fish	BAMM	If	Males	6	-2.542	0.768	0.5792	0.6722	-0.8282	0.1125	0.8078
Fish	DR	If	Males	6	-3.747	-0.186	0.0763	6.1418	-0.6986	0.0493	0.7044
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Males	5	—	—	—	0.7972	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgf	Males	5	-3.722	-1.044	0.0819	6.6959	-0.7196	0.0289	0.6147
Fish	BAMM	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	BAMM	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	DR	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of trait as a function of selection index (full dataset). Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	6	0.141	0.03	0.0514	11.5359	-0.8386	-0.0734	0.8435
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	16	-0.461	-0.142*	0.2571	0.1373	-0.2614	-0.0738	0.2694
All	SSD (length)	I	Males	9	0.044	-0.014	0.0802	12.5167	-0.8709	0.0211	0.8650
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	14	0.078	-0.142*†	0.3317	8.9161	-0.9415	-0.1054	0.9441
All	SSD (weight)	I	Males	41	-0.235	-0.104	0.0905	0.1915	-0.3462	0.0071	0.3734
All	SSD (length)	If	Males	9	0.041	-0.011	0.0392	11.2073	-0.8743	-0.0021	0.8750
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	12	0.013	-0.01	0.0264	10.2512	-0.8813	0.0575	0.8825
All	SSD (weight)	If	Males	34	-0.178	-0.037	0.0330	0.3193	-0.4610	0.0104	0.4826

Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of traits (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Trait	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	5	-0.309	0.044	0.0098	10.0368	-0.7339	0.0349	0.7733
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	6	0.057	-0.03	0.0597	14.6627	-0.8957	0.0350	0.9060
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	8	0.016	-0.016	0.0001	15.5371	-0.9117	0.0166	0.8790
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	22	-0.134	0.04	0.0051	0.4588	-0.5649	-0.0254	0.5534
All	SSD (length)	Is	Females	3	-0.239	-0.064	0.6439	13.6634	-0.9097	0.0120	0.9473
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	4	0.035	-0.026	0.3926	13.9362	-0.9143	-0.0746	0.9430
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	11	-0.441	-0.079	0.0132	0.2997	-0.3898	-0.0081	0.2827
All	SSD (length)	I	Females	8	0.006	0.004	0.0029	9.9099	-0.8066	-0.0701	0.8022
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	14	0.013	-0.021	0.1159	10.1796	-0.8962	-0.0027	0.8897
All	SSD (weight)	I	Females	35	-0.221	-0.049*†	0.1267	0.3164	-0.4777	-0.0370	0.4974
All	SSD (length)	If	Females	6	0.021	0.017	0.1319	12.9255	-0.9010	-0.0622	0.8709
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	11	-0.012	-0.01	0.0306	11.5163	-0.8754	-0.0524	0.8604
All	SSD (weight)	If	Females	32	-0.305	-0.047*†	0.1672	0.4023	-0.6644	-0.0965	0.6547
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	3	-0.022	0.128	0.8206	15.2506	-0.9416	-0.0786	0.9329
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	8	0.008	-0.011	0.0121	13.9453	-0.8987	-0.0159	0.9137
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	20	-0.198	-0.014	0.0170	0.6162	-0.6691	-0.0224	0.6471
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	—	—	—	—	12.5961	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Males	17	-0.168	-0.107*	0.3467	6.6475	-0.9237	0.0423	0.9216
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Males	15	-0.248	-0.082	0.2474	6.7571	-0.8838	0.0269	0.9017
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	9	-0.014	-0.035	0.0248	13.0333	-0.9072	-0.0023	0.8983
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	4	0.665	0.168	0.5903	12.8065	-0.9527	-0.0197	0.9340
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Females	16	-0.341	-0.046	0.1793	6.8326	-0.8681	-0.0164	0.8918
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Females	14	-0.511	-0.101	0.2314	8.6319	-0.8868	0.0713	0.9202
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	10.8492	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	3	0.001	0.002	0.0040	16.4319	-0.9387	0.1080	0.9314
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	6	-0.060	0.034	0.1011	12.6333	-0.8997	0.0186	0.8759
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Males	4	-0.119	0.084	0.0561	11.2626	-0.7508	0.0116	0.7228
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	6	-0.029	0.015	0.0501	17.7299	-0.9128	-0.0226	0.8913
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	9.4202	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	14.5431	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	12.3005	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	3	-0.031	-0.014	0.2981	11.8724	-0.9568	0.0936	0.9771
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	7	-0.022	-0.006	0.0168	11.9723	-0.8810	0.0872	0.8855
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Females	4	-0.066	-0.081	0.4669	10.2912	-0.8541	0.1738	0.8788
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	6	-0.037	-0.009	0.0248	12.7857	-0.8830	-0.0219	0.8618
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Females	4	-0.062	-0.115	0.4519	11.7883	-0.8754	-0.0143	0.8477
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of traits (continued)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	16.7960	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	14.5436	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	3	0.306	-0.174	0.3085	13.5588	-0.8935	-0.0993	0.8785
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	8	0.125	-0.073*†	0.6145	11.0389	-0.9805	-0.0119	0.9823
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	6	0.043	-0.033	0.6103	15.2402	-0.9063	-0.1573	0.9954
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	5	0.038	0.075	0.0074	13.5619	-0.9323	0.0219	0.9402
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	7	-0.004	-0.107*†	0.7595	13.8639	-0.9337	0.6786	0.9909
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	5	0.026	-0.005	0.0161	15.5882	-0.9004	0.0428	0.9400
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	5	0.008	-0.015	0.1391	16.8277	-0.9726	0.0253	0.9478
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	9	-0.668	-0.105	0.1095	0.2877	-0.2588	0.0111	0.3150
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.011	0.004	0.0538	15.1620	-0.9216	-0.0011	0.9194
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Males	18	-0.375	-0.142	0.1020	0.3258	-0.4641	-0.0234	0.4148
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.010	0.007	0.1047	15.5432	-0.9411	0.0341	0.9390
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Males	13	-0.435	0	0.0000	0.6322	-0.6059	-0.0016	0.6008
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	10	-0.311	0.716	0.2556	6.5652	-0.8454	0.0091	0.7906
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Females	3	-0.239	-0.064	0.6439	14.7580	-0.9154	0.0390	0.9359
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	6	-1.057	-0.228	0.1601	0.6511	-0.5894	-0.0428	0.6362
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Females	4	-0.016	0.015	0.0957	15.1286	-0.9428	-0.0131	0.9113
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Females	13	-0.513	-0.029	0.0372	0.5337	-0.5525	0.0019	0.5287
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Females	12	-0.624	-0.062	0.1480	5.6413	-0.7558	-0.0540	0.7720
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	7	-0.482	-0.25	0.0646	11.6480	-0.8532	0.0701	0.8886
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Males	—	—	—	—	15.3316	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Males	5	0.066	-0.005	0.0027	15.8074	-0.9236	-0.0643	0.9283
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S3. PGLS results for each combination of traits (continued)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	4	0.090	-0.047	0.2558	12.7557	-0.9558	0.0943	0.9674
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Females	4	-0.008	-0.053	0.2920	16.7617	-0.9443	-0.1169	0.9365
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Females	4	0.081	0.021	0.1651	15.1422	-0.9452	0.0133	0.9164
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Males	3	-2.026	-0.57	0.4106	11.9908	-0.8143	0.0076	0.8234
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Males	3	-2.955	-0.892	0.7234	12.6746	-0.9359	-0.0650	0.9043
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Males	3	-1.701	-0.419	0.3704	14.7231	-0.8741	0.0667	0.8751
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Males	11	0.516	-0.127	0.0198	0.1935	-0.2142	-0.0006	0.1629
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Males	11	0.278	0.056	0.0108	0.3847	-0.3957	0.0037	0.4044
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Males	11	0.309	-0.199	0.0746	0.3010	-0.2924	-0.0379	0.3098
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Males	9	0.727	0.029	0.0013	0.1929	-0.2135	-0.0006	0.1761
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Males	9	0.645	0.241	0.2350	0.4261	-0.5430	0.0662	0.5535
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Males	9	0.592	0.091	0.0190	0.3125	-0.3123	-0.0194	0.3024
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Males	4	0.682	0.049	0.0010	6.4541	-0.4873	-0.0022	0.5303
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Males	4	0.338	0.048	0.0018	9.0851	-0.6527	-0.0508	0.6326
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Males	4	0.685	-0.439	0.0694	6.9739	-0.6269	-0.0091	0.5465
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Females	3	-1.815	-0.518	0.8313	15.8206	-0.9383	0.0699	0.9372
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Females	3	-2.211	-0.666	0.9897	12.0101	-0.9838	-0.0798	0.9910
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Females	3	-1.582	-0.393	0.7993	16.1932	-0.9262	-0.0810	0.9548
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Females	10	0.810	0.178	0.0517	0.2043	-0.1876	0.0183	0.2307
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Females	10	0.315	0.008	0.0003	0.3924	-0.4189	0.0068	0.3439
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Females	10	0.260	-0.055	0.0078	0.2892	-0.3273	-0.0407	0.2893
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Females	8	0.765	0.251	0.0418	0.3740	-0.2912	0.0215	0.3066
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Females	8	0.218	-0.009	0.0001	0.4524	-0.3729	-0.0208	0.4031
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Females	8	0.545	0.111	0.0069	0.3669	-0.3359	0.0011	0.3073
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.989	-0.508	0.7598	0.8605	-0.9014	-0.1257	0.8682
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	8.5268	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.803	-0.534	0.6919	0.7525	-0.8031	0.1116	0.8439

Table S4. PGLS results for each combination of trait as a function of selection index (including only studies that clearly reported zero-success individuals - "zero-only dataset"). Slopes with an asterisk (*) refer to models where the slope's p-value, as calculated by the caper package, is smaller than 0.05. Slopes with a dagger (†) refer to models with $\Delta AICc > 2$ in relation to a null model with just the intercept. Bold lines highlight PGLS with any of these two statistical supports. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	4	0.153	-0.005	0.0035	12.3160	-0.8777	0.0483	0.8579
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	13	-0.492	-0.127	0.1683	0.1360	-0.2093	0.0316	0.2090
All	SSD (length)	I	Males	8	0.039	-0.007	0.0114	14.2880	-0.8900	0.0340	0.8603
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	11	0.094	-0.052*	0.3626	8.8195	-0.9404	0.0244	0.9454
All	SSD (weight)	I	Males	28	-0.272	-0.108	0.0723	0.2065	-0.3066	-0.0037	0.3556
All	SSD (length)	If	Males	8	0.037	-0.003	0.0016	13.5814	-0.8722	-0.0062	0.8666
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	9	-0.003	0.005	0.0028	10.8551	-0.8531	0.0238	0.8306
All	SSD (weight)	If	Males	22	-0.209	-0.022	0.0067	0.4448	-0.5008	0.0158	0.5214
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	PGLS				Empirical			Power analysis			
	Trait	index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	3	-0.451	0.873	0.6530	15.5371	-0.8886	0.0361	0.9242
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	5	0.056	-0.046	0.0129	14.4141	-0.9017	-0.0332	0.8863
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	7	0.016	0.12	0.0042	11.2783	-0.8563	-0.0657	0.9017
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	16	-0.164	0.597	0.1566	0.6666	-0.7543	-0.0686	0.7548
All	SSD (length)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	—	—	—	—	15.7472	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	I	Females	3	0.013	0.006	0.9630	12.6437	-0.9342	-0.0093	0.9190
All	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	9	0.006	-0.062*	0.4803	9.8660	-0.9739	0.2187	0.9636
All	SSD (weight)	I	Females	16	-0.236	-0.052*†	0.3558	0.6206	-0.8311	-0.2101	0.8330
All	SSD (length)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	8	-0.009	-0.023	0.1097	12.8698	-0.8589	0.0321	0.8992
All	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	0.6120	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
All	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	7	0.014	0.007	0.0005	13.6755	-0.8499	-0.0642	0.9132
All	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	12	-0.241	-0.105	0.0522	5.8680	-0.7008	-0.0010	0.6852
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	5	-0.058	0.033	0.0874	14.3976	-0.9187	0.0514	0.8636
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Males	4	-0.119	0.084	0.0561	10.2808	-0.7961	-0.0118	0.7054
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	5	-0.033	0.019	0.0376	13.1315	-0.8974	-0.0372	0.8982
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	10.7702	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	13.9908	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	—	—	—	—	12.6973	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	4	-0.015	-0.044	0.2108	15.4115	-0.9185	0.1929	0.9354
Squamates	SSD (weight)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	13.9048	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	4	-0.015	-0.036	0.1298	14.9350	-0.9133	0.0506	0.8908
Squamates	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	14.3075	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	14.4422	—	—	—
Squamates	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	—	—	—	—	12.7857	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	6	0.143	-0.058	0.6562	12.2051	-0.9740	0.3166	0.9702
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	4	0.016	-0.013	0.0845	17.2918	-0.9390	0.0715	0.9283
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	4	0.017	0.181	0.0800	15.5467	-0.9316	-0.0743	0.9371
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	5	-0.006	-0.068	0.7356	13.9250	-0.9794	-0.1875	0.9718
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	4	0.009	0.005	0.0342	12.9577	-0.9155	0.0607	0.9400
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Amphibians	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	4	0.028	0.044	0.2954	13.7745	-0.9621	-0.0845	0.9415
Amphibians	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	8	-0.779	-0.065	0.0365	0.2906	-0.2473	-0.0070	0.2149
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.012	0.003	0.0232	17.1587	-0.8923	-0.0280	0.9302
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Males	14	-0.426	-0.113	0.0548	0.3690	-0.4528	-0.0194	0.4358
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.010	0.007	0.1047	14.8044	-0.9322	0.0521	0.9656
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Males	10	-0.531	0.073	0.2092	8.4434	-0.8377	-0.0176	0.8302
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	9	-0.376	0.729	0.3430	9.9087	-0.9183	0.0239	0.9238
Mammals	SSD (length)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	I	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	I	Females	7	-0.402	-0.088	0.4822	10.6679	-0.9109	0.1140	0.9191
Mammals	SSD (length)	If	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	If	Females	7	-0.347	-0.127	0.5545	10.2504	-0.9688	-0.1960	0.9465
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mammals	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	5	-0.461	0.225	0.0165	12.5224	-0.8460	0.0417	0.8638
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Males	4	0.060	-0.013	0.0143	15.9413	-0.9404	-0.0875	0.9354
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Males	4	0.072	0.019	0.0177	18.3807	-0.8981	0.0730	0.9241
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	3	0.116	0.105	0.0694	15.8103	-0.9477	-0.0274	0.9405
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	I	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	If	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Fish	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Males	4	-0.149	-0.018	0.1275	16.4027	-0.9175	0.0684	0.9126
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Males	9	-0.330	-0.094*	0.4792	10.8696	-0.9628	-0.1868	0.9483
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Males	—	—	—	—	10.1280	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S4. PGLS results for each combination (continued)

Clade	Trait	PGLS			Empirical			Power analysis			
		index	Sex	Sample size	intercept	slope	R ²	Threshold	Q = 0.025	Median	Q = 0.975
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Males	4	-0.157	-0.353	0.0567	13.7158	-0.9205	0.0105	0.9143
Birds	SSD (length)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Is	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	I	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	I	Females	6	-0.226	-0.047	0.3332	12.7333	-0.9450	0.0606	0.9204
Birds	SSD (length)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	If	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	If	Females	—	—	—	—	12.7550	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (length)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (SVL)	Bgf	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	SSD (weight)	Bgf	Females	4	-0.133	-0.023	0.0284	14.0889	-0.9450	0.0103	0.9021
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Males	6	0.248	0.14	0.1246	0.4817	-0.5445	-0.0399	0.4958
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Males	6	0.180	0.339	0.5374	0.6121	-0.7383	-0.0436	0.6941
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Males	6	0.019	0.181	0.4516	0.7801	-0.7875	-0.1817	0.7964
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Males	4	0.409	-0.025	0.0069	4.5498	-0.4351	-0.0312	0.4582
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Males	4	0.327	0.331	0.6213	5.1029	-0.6490	0.1042	0.7599
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Males	4	0.112	0.142	0.3390	6.4243	-0.7272	0.0744	0.6949
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Males	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Males	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Is	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	12.3305	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	12.1441	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	I	Females	—	—	—	—	14.6567	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	If	Females	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgm	Females	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (col. discr.)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (PCA)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Birds	Dichr. (seg. class.)	Bgf	Females	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Table S5. "Background" phylogenetic signal and continuous character evolution results of sexual selection intensity, some traits that are used in the literature as proxies for sexual selection, and body size for all vertebrates, separated by sex when appropriate. Estimates in bold (and also with an asterisk) refer to significant phylogenetic signal (i.e., close from $\lambda = 1$, or different from random permutations of the data in the phylogeny, in the case of Blomberg's K, Abouheif's C, and Moran's I). All data were log-transformed at base 2 before analysis. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; BGF = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index

Index	Sex	Best Model	Phylo Signal	Estimate	Sample size
Bgf	Females	WN	Blomberg's K	0.06585	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Pagel's lambda	0.06646	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Moran's I	-0.07436	32
Bgf	Females	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.05325	32
Bgf	Males	OU	Blomberg's K	0.10096	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.15496	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Moran's I	0.28816*	36
Bgf	Males	OU	Abouheif's C	0.29832*	36
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Blomberg's K	1.02739	3
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Pagel's lambda	5e-05	3

Table S5. "Background" phylogenetic signal and continuous character evolution results of sexual selection intensity, some traits that are used in the literature as proxies for sexual selection, and body size for all vertebrates, separated by sex when appropriate. Estimates in bold (and also with an asterisk) refer to significant phylogenetic signal (i.e., close from $\lambda = 1$, or different from random permutations of the data in the phylogeny, in the case of Blomberg's K, Abouheif's C, and Moran's I). All data were log-transformed at base 2 before analysis. Legend: All = all vertebrate orders; Bgf = Bateman gradients calculated from fertilization success; Bgm = Bateman gradients calculated from mating success; Is = Opportunity for sexual selection; If = Opportunity for selection calculated from fertilization success; I = Opportunity for selection calculated from reproductive success; SSD = Sexual size Dimorphism; Dichro - Dichromatism; seg. class. = segment classification; col. discr. = color discriminability index (*continued*)

Index	Sex	Best Model	Phylo Signal	Estimate	Sample size
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Moran's I	-0.44694	3
Bgm	Females	OU & EB	Abouheif's C	0.07959	3
Bgm	Males	WN	Blomberg's K	0.17252	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Pagel's lambda	7e-05	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Moran's I	-0.47826	6
Bgm	Males	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.24665	6
I	Females	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.09481	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.01115	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.02577	55
I	Females	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.0412	55
I	Males	OU	Blomberg's K	0.10721*	62
I	Males	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.74129	62
I	Males	OU	Moran's I	0.24496*	62
I	Males	OU	Abouheif's C	0.2588*	62
If	Females	OU	Blomberg's K	0.20886*	48
If	Females	OU	Pagel's lambda	0.24203	48
If	Females	OU	Moran's I	0.08263	48
If	Females	OU	Abouheif's C	0.10662	48
If	Males	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.09102	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.21714	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.13976	53
If	Males	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.15811	53
Is	Females	WN	Blomberg's K	0.13755	15
Is	Females	WN	Pagel's lambda	7e-05	15
Is	Females	WN	Moran's I	-0.14237	15
Is	Females	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.06595	15
Is	Males	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.11154	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Pagel's lambda	0.09555	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.19825	21
Is	Males	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.22608	21
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Blomberg's K	0.04372	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Pagel's Lambda	0.90765*	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Moran's I	0.33312*	53
SSD (weight)	All	OU	Abouheif's C	0.34241*	53
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.48203	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	0.20092	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Moran's I	0.10995	17
SSD (SVL)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	0.14751	17
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Blomberg's K	0.10272	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Pagel's Lambda	0.18908	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Moran's I	0.00203	12
SSD (length)	All	OU & WN	Abouheif's C	0.10478	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Blomberg's K	0.50311	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Moran's I	-0.07374	12
Dichro (PCA)	All	BM & WN	Abouheif's C	0.03922	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.38389	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Moran's I	-0.2309	12
Dichro (seg. class.)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.15946	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Blomberg's K	0.21853	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Pagel's Lambda	7e-05	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Moran's I	-0.10125	12
Dichro (col. discr.)	All	WN	Abouheif's C	-0.06351	12
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Blomberg's K	0.694958263895248*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Pagel's Lambda	1.00164128866343*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Moran's I	0.651426488813106*	53
Body weight	All	BM & OU	Abouheif's C	0.678858376979092*	53

Table S6. Summary of significant analyses, per the p-value of the slope (Hypothesis tested: significantly different from zero). Legend: Bgf = Fertilization-based Bateman gradient; Bgm = Mating-based Bateman gradient; I = Mating success index; If = fertilization success index; I = Reproductive success index.

Clade	Sex	Independent variable	Predicted variable	Dataset	Sample size	Effect
Fish	Females	Bgf	DR	full	7	Positive

Table S6. Summary of significant analyses, per the p-value of the slope (Hypothesis tested: significantly different from zero). Legend: Bgf = Fertilization-based Bateman gradient; Bgm = Mating-based Bateman gradient; I = Mating success index; If = fertilization success index; I = Reproduction (*continued*)

Clade	Sex	Independent variable	Predicted variable	Dataset	Sample size	Effect
Birds	Males	Is	DR	full	6	Positive
Amphibians	Males	Is	BAMM	full	3	Positive
Amphibians	Females	I	BAMM	full	7	Negative
All	Males	Bgf	BAMM	zero-only	25	Positive
Birds	Males	Is	DR	zero-only	4	Negative
Amphibians	Females	I	BAMM	zero-only	5	Negative
Fish	Males	I	BAMM	zero-only	6	Positive
All	Males	Is	SSD (weight)	full	16	Negative
All	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	full	14	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (weight)	full	35	Negative
All	Females	If	SSD (weight)	full	32	Negative
Birds	Males	I	SSD (weight)	full	17	Negative
Amphibians	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	full	8	Negative
Amphibians	Females	I	SSD (SVL)	full	7	Negative
All	Males	I	SSD (SVL)	zero-only	11	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (SVL)	zero-only	9	Negative
All	Females	I	SSD (weight)	zero-only	16	Negative
Birds	Males	I	SSD (weight)	zero-only	9	Negative

Table S7. Deviance tables of log2 DR speciation rates explained by different taxonomic groups.

Factor	DF	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	P value
Clade	4	6877.0	1719.26	4209.2207	< 2.2e-16
Tax. Family	947	16456.9	17.38	42.5460	< 2.2e-16
Genus	6074	13448.0	2.21	5.4205	< 2.2e-16
Residual	21058	8601.1	0.41	—	

Table S8. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).

Dataset	Speciation rate estimate	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Full dataset	DR	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	DR	Birds	Females	4
Full dataset	DR	Birds	Males	3
Full dataset	DR	Fish	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Fish	Males	3
Full dataset	DR	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	DR	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	DR	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	DR	Squamates	Males	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Birds	Females	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Birds	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Fish	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Fish	Males	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	BAMM	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	BAMM	Squamates	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Birds	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Birds	Males	2
Zero-only	DR	Fish	Females	0
Zero-only	DR	Fish	Males	3
Zero-only	DR	Mammals	Females	3
Zero-only	DR	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only	DR	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only	DR	Squamates	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Birds	Females	3
Zero-only	BAMM	Birds	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Fish	Females	0
Zero-only	BAMM	Fish	Males	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Mammals	Females	3

Table S8. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).
(continued)

Dataset	Speciation rate estimate	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Zero-only	BAMM	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only	BAMM	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only	BAMM	Squamates	Males	2

Table S9. Number of selection indices correlated with speciation rate for different sub-clades of vertebrates and sexes (Both datasets). See details on parameters and sample size (number of species per analyses) in Supplementary table 1 (Full dataset) and 2 (zero-only dataset).

Dataset	Operationalization of SSD	Clade	Sex	Indices tested (out of 5 possible)
Full dataset	Length	Fish	Females	2
Full dataset	Length	Fish	Males	2
Full dataset	Length	Mammals	Females	2
Full dataset	Length	Mammals	Males	2
Full dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Females	3
Full dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Males	4
Full dataset	SVL	Squamates	Females	3
Full dataset	SVL	Squamates	Males	3
Full dataset	Weight	Birds	Females	3
Full dataset	Weight	Birds	Males	3
Full dataset	Weight	Mammals	Females	4
Full dataset	Weight	Mammals	Males	4
Full dataset	Weight	Squamates	Females	2
Full dataset	Weight	Squamates	Males	1
Zero-only dataset	Length	Fish	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	Length	Mammals	Males	2
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Females	3
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Amphibians	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Squamates	Females	2
Zero-only dataset	SVL	Squamates	Males	2
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Birds	Females	2
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Birds	Males	3
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Mammals	Females	3
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Mammals	Males	4
Zero-only dataset	Weight	Squamates	Males	1